

ment period, and growth index on varieties TAPL #796, IR36, and TN1. TAPL #796 and IR36 have the *Glh* 6 gene for resistance.

Thirty-day-old potted plants of the test varieties were enclosed with 10- × 90-cm mylar film cages and arranged in a randomized complete block design on a water tray in the greenhouse. Each variety was replicated 10 times with 1 pot equaling 1 replication.

Plants in each cage were infested with 10 first-instar GLH nymphs from the respective colonies and regularly observed for the emergence of adults. When adults emerged, the date was recorded and the insects were counted and removed from the cage once a day until adult emergence was complete. The total number of adults that emerged from each cage was determined and percentage survival was computed as

$$\frac{\text{number of adults that emerged}}{\text{number of nymphs infested}} \times 100$$

The mean developmental period (1st instar to adult) on each variety was calcu-

Survival, development period, and growth index of 2 GLH colonies on 3 rice varieties,^a IRRI.

Variety	Survival (%)		Development period (d)		Growth index	
	TAPL #796	TN1	TAPL #796	TN1	TAPL #796	TN1
TAPL #796	90.0 ab	50 c	15.5 c	20.0 a	5.80 a	2.57 b
IR36	57.5 bc	74 abc	17.5 b	19.9 a	3.27 b	3.73 b
TN1	88.0 ab	100 a	14 c	15.8 c	6.04 a	6.12 a

^aUnder each parameter, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at the 5% level.

lated and the growth index was computed as

$$\frac{\% \text{ survival}}{\text{mean development period (d)}}$$

Survival of the TAPL #796 was significantly higher than that of the TN1 colony on TAPL #796 (see table). There was no significant difference between the two colonies on IR36 and TN1, and survival of the TAPL #796 colony on TAPL #796 and IR36 did not differ significantly. Development of the TAPL #796 colony was significantly shorter than that of the TN1 colony on TAPL #796 and IR36, but no difference was observed on TN1. The growth index of the colonies significantly

differed only on TAPL #796. The growth index of the TAPL #796 colony was significantly higher on TAPL #796 than on IR36.

The results indicate a degree of insect adaptation to TAPL #796 after 18 generations on the variety. Although TAPL #796 and IR36 have the same gene for GLH resistance, these varieties may have different levels of resistance to the insect or may possess minor genes, which result in little cross adaptation, as indicated by the differences in the reaction of the TAPL #796 colony. □

A new brown planthopper (BPH) resistant rice for Pondicherry, India

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Land in the Union Territory, Pondicherry, is intensively cropped with a rice-based multiple cropping system, which has increased pest problems. BPH *Nilaparvata lugens* is a major pest from Jun to Sep, and causes 30-40% damage to the rice crop. Recommended controls have not solved the problem. Almost all varieties grown are highly susceptible to BPH.

We identified BPHR-5 (IR13427-45-2) as having BPH resistance and good yield potential. BPHR-5 is a multiple cross of IR3403-267, IR36, and Ptb 33, and is rated 3 for BPH resistance, based on the Standard Evaluation System for Rice (SES).

BPHR-5 is a medium-dwarf, 95-cm-tall variety. Tillers are semierect, compact, and lodging resistant. It matures in 115-

Table 1. BPH resistance and yield potentials of BPHR-5 in Pondicherry, India.

Site	Yield (t/ha)				Resistance to BPH ^a			
	BPHR-5	IR50	Vaigai	PY2	BPHR-5	IR50	Vaigai	PY2
Lawspet	5.8	—	—	2.1	3	9	9	5
Adingapattu	5.9	—	4.7	—	1	—	3	—
T. N. Palayam	6.8	5.4	—	5.5	1	3	—	3
Mettupalayam	5.1	—	4.5	5.0	3	—	3	3
KVK Farm	5.2	3.7	1.1	4.5	1	5	7	3

^aBy the 1980 SES scale.

120 d when transplanted and grows well in navarai and sornavari seasons. The boot leaf is slightly broad and semierect with late senescence. Grains are coarse, long-slender, with a 5.28 length-breadth ratio. They are opaque white and 1,000 weight is 25 g. BPHR-5 yields 4.8 t/ha in farmer fields and produces better than other varieties tested (Table 1, 2). In one area with heavy BPH pressure, BPHR-5 yielded 5.8 t/ha versus 0.0 for Vaigai and 0.2 for PY2.

After performance trials, BPHR-5 was approved for release as BPH-resistant variety Pondicherry 3 (PY3) by the State Seed Subcommittee of Pondicherry. □

Table 2. Mean yield of BPHR-5 in outstation trials, Pondicherry, India.

Site	Yield (t/ha)	
	BPHR-5	Vaigai
Bhavanisagar	7.3	5.7
Ambasamudram	4.6	4.6
Paiyur	4.2	4.1
Perumangudi	6.8	—
Vilangudi	7.5	—
Viswanathapuram	6.7	—

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